

Induced Breeding and Embryonic Development of *Macrogathus aral* (Bloch & Schneider, 1801) under Captive Conditions

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Abstract: This study investigated captive breeding and embryonic development of *Macrogathus aral*, a promising food and ornamental fish from Indian freshwater systems, using graded GnRHa (Ovatide) doses across 1:1, 2:1, and 3:1 sex ratio in triplicate trials with 162 broodfish (108 males, 54 females) from Kangsabati River. Optimal results emerged at 0.6 ml/kg for males and 0.8 ml/kg for females in the 2:1 ratio, yielding peak fertilization ($91.05 \pm 1.07\%$) and hatching rates ($89.89 \pm 2.02\%$) after 15 h latency period ($P < 0.05$), while controls and extreme doses yielded no spawning. Spawning and embryonic development proceeded predictably at 27.9-28.3°C water temperature, with fertilized eggs (1.25-1.60 mm diameter) advancing post-fertilization through organogenesis featuring a defined embryonic axis and cardiac pulsations at 25.20-25.50 h, followed by hatching at 30.47-35.10 h that produced 2.28 ± 0.16 mm larvae initially quiescent before active air-gulping and heart rates of 103-109 beats/min. These findings establish a viable protocol for artificial propagation of *M. aral*, providing essential baseline data to enhance seed production, conservation of wild stocks, and sustainable propagation in declining natural populations.

Keywords: *Macrogathus aral*, Induced breeding, Synthetic hormone, Dose optimization, Embryonic development

Introduction:

Macrogathus aral, commonly known as the One Stripe Spiny Eel, belongs to the family Mastacembelidae, which is distributed across various freshwater habitats, primarily in Southeast Asia and the Indian subcontinent [1]. In the Indian subcontinent, this species is valued as both a staple food fish among rural populations and an ornamental species cherished for its attractive coloration and playful behavior. Among the Mastacembeliformes, *M. aral* is frequently encountered and goes by the local name 'Pankal' [2] in West Bengal. *M. aral* was last evaluated for the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species in 2010 and was categorized as Least Concern (LC), indicating a favorable conservation status [3].

In recent decades, global aquaculture has entered a dynamic phase marked by increasing demands for animal protein, driving significant advancements in fisheries research and the development of innovative seed production techniques. Among these, induced spawning has emerged as a key technology, contributing substantially to the expansion of cultured stocks in several commercially important fish groups such as carps, catfish, and tilapia. However, there remains a lack of documented research on the application of synthetic hormones for induced breeding in *M. aral* in India. A thorough understanding of embryonic development is fundamental for advancing fish reproductive biology and supporting conservation and aquaculture practices. This knowledge aids in creating optimal conditions for artificial propagation, large-scale seed production, and habitat management. Although *M. aral* holds ecological and aquaculture importance, detailed information on its embryonic development under captive conditions remains scarce. With natural reproduction rates declining, there is a pressing need to develop standardized breeding protocols. Insight into developmental stages and organogenesis is critical for improving hatchery performance and ensuring sustainable seed production.

Despite growing interest in *M. aral*, comprehensive knowledge regarding its breeding performance remains scarce, highlighting an urgent need for targeted research to address these gaps. Effective management of natural populations and the development of artificial propagation techniques are essential for the species conservation. In this context, the present study was undertaken to evaluate the feasibility of captive breeding and embryonic development of *M. aral*. The findings are expected to contribute valuable insights toward species management and long-term conservation strategies. Establishing a standardized protocol for captive breeding could significantly reduce spawning intervals, enhance seed production within a shorter time period, and support both commercial aquaculture and the preservation of wild stocks.

Materials and methods:

Study area and broodstock management:

The study was conducted at the outdoor culture unit of the Department of Fishery Sciences, Vidyasagar University, from September 2022 to August 2023, during which a total of 162 specimens of *Macrogathus aral* (108 males and 54 females) were collected from the Kangsabati River, Paschim Medinipur district, West Bengal. Following collection, the fish were acclimatized in the outdoor unit, and maintained in four cemented tanks (4 × 3 × 4 ft; 450 L capacity each). Fish were fed a formulated diet at 5% of their body weight per day. To simulate natural benthic and burrowing behavior, sand substrate was introduced, along with native aquatic macrophytes (*Eichhornia crassipes*) to provide habitat complexity. Water quality parameters were monitored regularly following [4] guidelines. Broodstock selection was based on secondary sexual characteristics. Mature females showed a brownish-yellow dorsum, yellow ventrum, distended abdomen, and a prominent fleshy genital papilla with a visible oviduct. Males were slenderer, with brown dorsal coloration, pale yellowish-brown ventrum, and a relatively smaller genital papilla; milt release upon gentle abdominal pressure confirmed maturity [5].

Experimental design:

Sexually mature male and female broodfish of *M. aral* were initially segregated from the rearing tanks and placed in plastic containers for a brief acclimatization period prior to hormone administration. Thereafter, the broodfish were transferred to the outdoor culture unit of the Department of Fishery Sciences, where six rectangular glass aquaria (24" × 12" × 12") had previously been conditioned with 40 L of dechlorinated

water and maintained under stable conditions for three days before the onset of hormone induction trials. To evaluate the effect of sex ratio and hormone dosage on breeding performance, three experimental combinations were established with different male-to-female ratios: 1:1 (E1), 2:1 (E2), and 3:1 (E3). Each experiment was paired with a corresponding control group to validate the results. Five graded concentrations of the synthetic hormone Ovotide were tested across these setups and designated as treatments T1, T2, T3, T4, and T5. All treatments were conducted in triplicate to ensure reproducibility and allow for statistical validation of the outcomes.

Induced breeding procedure:

GnRHa (Ovotide) was administered intramuscularly at an approximate 45° angle near the base of the dorsal or pectoral fins. Hormone dosage was determined individually according to the body weight of each brood fish and prepared immediately prior to injection. After hormone treatment, brooders were transferred to separate glass aquaria with male-to-female ratios of 1:1, 2:1, and 3:1. Continuous aeration was provided in all tanks to maintain optimum water quality. Water hyacinth (*Eichhornia crassipes*) was supplied as a natural spawning substrate to support adhesion of fertilized adhesive eggs during oviposition.

Breeding performance and embryonic development observation:

Following ovulation, the eggs of *M. aral* were observed adhering to the fibrous roots of water hyacinth. Under microscopic examination, fertilized eggs appeared transparent with a clearly visible nucleus, while unfertilized ones exhibited a dark brown coloration. The effective fecundity of each female was estimated by randomly sampling the spawned eggs, and the total egg count along with fertilization rates were assessed as per the methodology described by [6].

Fertilization rate was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Fertilization rate (\%)} = \frac{\text{Number of fertilized eggs}}{\text{Total number of eggs}} \times 100$$

and hatching rate was determined as:

$$\text{Hatching rate (\%)} = \frac{\text{Number of hatchlings}}{\text{Total number of fertilized eggs}} \times 100$$

Embryonic development was monitored using a photomicrographic microscope (Carl Zeiss Microscopy GmbH, 37081, Göttingen, Germany). Observations were carried out every 5-10 minutes up to the morula stage, and subsequently at 30-minute intervals until hatching. The microscope's imaging system was employed to measure the diameter of eggs. All developmental stages and their characteristics were validated following protocols outlined by [7] and [8].

Statistical analysis:

All data were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD). Statistical significance ($P < 0.05$) was determined using one-way ANOVA in Microsoft Excel (ver. 2019).

Results:

A total of 162 brood fish (108 males and 54 females) were utilized for captive rearing and induced breeding trials of *Macrogathus aral*. The effects of different hormonal doses and sex ratios on fertilization rate, latency period, and hatching success are presented in Tables 1 - 3. No spawning occurred in the control groups lacking hormonal treatment. Following GnRHa administration, brooders exhibited distinct courtship and mating behaviors within 8-14 hours post-injection. The latency period varied significantly across treatments, with successful spawning achieved between 15 and 18 hours in different experimental setups. In experiment E1, fertilization occurred in treatment T3 (70.24 \pm 3.63) and T4 (68.63 \pm 1.96), while no fertilization was observed in other doses (Table 1). In E2, the fertilization rate was significantly highest in T3 (91.05 \pm 1.07) and lowest in T1 (84.28 \pm 1.21), with no fertilization in the control and T5 (Table 2). In E3, fertilization was recorded only in T2, T3, and T4, with T3 showing the maximum rate (80.86 \pm 1.66%) (Table 3). Across all experiments, T3 of E2 exhibited the highest fertilization rate ($P < 0.05$). Overall,

fertilization rates in E2 were significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) than those in E1 and E3. The hatching rate in E2 was significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) than in E1 and E3, with the highest value in T3 ($89.89 \pm 2.02\%$) at a male-to-female ratio of 2:1.

Table 1. Captive breeding experiment of *M. aral* (M: F=1:1) using GnRH α (Experiment 1)

Treatments	Males		Females		Hormonal doses (ml/kg body weight)		Latency period (Hrs.)	Fertilization Rate (%)	Hatching Rate (%)
	BW (g)	TL (cm)	BW (g)	TL (cm)	M	F			
Control	28.14 \pm 2.53	21.60 \pm 0.90	36.29 \pm 2.38	25.03 \pm 1.62	-	-	-	-	-
T1	30.95 \pm 2.06	22.80 \pm 0.75	31.75 \pm 3.73	22.00 \pm 2.55	0.2	0.4	-	-	-
T2	27.33 \pm 1.68	21.40 \pm 0.70	32.48 \pm 0.63	22.37 \pm 0.47	0.4	0.6	-	-	-
T3	32.17 \pm 1.93	22.97 \pm 0.86	31.61 \pm 1.80	22.10 \pm 1.00	0.6	0.8	18	70.24 \pm 3.63	72.70 \pm 2.35
T4	27.14 \pm 0.36	21.10 \pm 0.30	31.57 \pm 1.32	21.73 \pm 0.93	0.8	1.0	18	68.63 \pm 1.96	67.03 \pm 1.67
T5	26.61 \pm 2.72	20.93 \pm 1.00	32.14 \pm 1.86	22.27 \pm 0.95	1.0	1.2	-	-	-

Table 2. Captive breeding experiment of *M. aral* (M: F=2:1) using GnRH α (Experiment 2)

Treatments	Males		Females		Hormonal doses (ml/kg body weight)		Latency period (Hrs.)	Fertilization Rate (%)	Hatching Rate (%)
	BW (g)	TL (cm)	BW (g)	TL (cm)	M	F			
Control	28.80 \pm 1.39	21.57 \pm 0.49	29.61 \pm 2.74	20.83 \pm 1.31	-	-	-	-	-
T1	30.71 \pm 2.29	22.75 \pm 1.55	30.11 \pm 1.17	20.97 \pm 0.65	0.2	0.4	18	84.28 \pm 1.21	85.04 \pm 1.45
T2	30.38 \pm 3.20	22.45 \pm 1.68	30.87 \pm 2.34	21.40 \pm 1.31	0.4	0.6	16	86.67 \pm 2.26	85.24 \pm 2.52
T3	31.84 \pm 2.82	23.02 \pm 1.76	32.02 \pm 1.46	22.07 \pm 1.01	0.6	0.8	15	91.05 \pm 1.07	89.89 \pm 2.02
T4	31.43 \pm 2.59	21.85 \pm 1.37	31.64 \pm 0.61	21.73 \pm 0.45	0.8	1.0	16	88.65 \pm 1.16	87.86 \pm 1.83
T5	30.56 \pm 3.60	22.35 \pm 1.53	30.95 \pm 1.38	21.43 \pm 0.91	1.0	1.2	-	-	-

Table 3. Captive breeding experiment of *M. aral* (M: F=3:1) using GnRH α (Experiment 3)

Treatments	Males		Females		Hormonal doses (ml/kg body weight)		Latency period (Hrs.)	Fertilization Rate (%)	Hatching Rate (%)
	BW (g)	TL (cm)	BW (g)	TL (cm)	M	F			
Control	25.15 \pm 3.05	20.03 \pm 1.94	30.29 \pm 2.23	21.07 \pm 1.16	-	-	-	-	-
T1	30.66 \pm 3.46	22.28 \pm 1.68	31.70 \pm 1.37	21.77 \pm 0.95	0.2	0.4	-	-	-
T2	31.93 \pm 2.69	22.73 \pm 1.40	30.09 \pm 1.60	20.70 \pm 1.05	0.4	0.6	18	75.09 \pm 2.47	78.96 \pm 1.06
T3	32.74 \pm 2.47	23.30 \pm 1.40	32.73 \pm 1.78	22.63 \pm 1.30	0.6	0.8	16	80.86 \pm 1.66	82.73 \pm 1.94
T4	27.46 \pm 4.07	21.68 \pm 1.96	31.65 \pm 1.30	21.80 \pm 0.92	0.8	1.0	16	78.56 \pm 0.63	82.04 \pm 1.63
T5	32.56 \pm 2.79	23.40 \pm 1.21	31.21 \pm 1.51	21.53 \pm 1.03	1.0	1.2	-	-	-

Water quality parameters-including temperature, salinity, pH, dissolved oxygen (DO), free CO₂, total alkalinity, and total hardness-in aquaria subjected to various treatments with *M. aral* were monitored and summarized in Table 4. Mean values of these parameters showed no significant differences ($P < 0.05$) across the experimental treatments.

Table 4. Water quality parameters in different experiments under GnRH α treatments

Experiments	Temperature (°C)	Salinity (ppt)	pH	DO (ppm)	Free CO ₂ (ppm)	Alkalinity (ppm)	Total Hardness (ppm)
E1	28.1 \pm 0.15	0.021 \pm 0.005	7.92 \pm 0.08	5.82 \pm 0.12	2.14 \pm 0.09	92.3 \pm 2.1	96.4 \pm 3.6
E2	27.9 \pm 0.18	0.018 \pm 0.004	7.78 \pm 0.11	5.67 \pm 0.15	2.26 \pm 0.10	88.7 \pm 1.8	91.2 \pm 4.1
E3	28.3 \pm 0.14	0.025 \pm 0.006	8.12 \pm 0.07	5.95 \pm 0.10	1.98 \pm 0.08	95.6 \pm 2.4	102.8 \pm 3.2

Embryonic development stages (Table 5) of *M. aral* unfolded progressively from zygote formation at 0 h, marked by an adhesive, demersal, spherical, and transparent egg, through perivitelline space emergence (0.15-0.19 h), cleavage initiation with blastodisc and oil globule aggregation at the animal pole (0.30 h), followed by 2-cell (0.54-0.59 h), 8-cell with unequal blastomeres (2.05-2.15 h), 16-cell (2.35-2.40 h), and rapid progression to 32, 64, and 128 cell stages (3.00-4.25 h); the morula cap enlarged at the animal pole (6.40-6.50 h), transitioning to a compressed blastula with indistinct marginal boundaries (10.45-11.05 h), then gastrulation featuring yolk invasion by a thin blastoderm layer, germinal ring development, embryonic shield visibility, and ½ to ¾ yolk coverage (15.00-15.30 h). Organogenesis advanced with a defined embryonic axis, completed yolk penetration, distinct head-tail regions, evident notochord, and cardiac

pulsations (25.20-25.50 h), culminating in hatching via intensified embryonic contortions that ruptured the egg envelope (30.47-35.10 h). Newly hatched *M. aral* larvae measured 2.28 ± 0.16 mm in total length. Initially quiescent, these larvae rested among aquatic vegetation or clung to aquarium walls and substrate; within 8-10 h post-hatch, they grew highly active, periodically surfacing to gulp air. The heart was barely visible but beat at 103-109 times per minute. Table 5 outlines the specifics of each embryonic stage, including their respective timings, while Figure 1 presents photographs of these distinct developmental phases.

Table 5. Different phases of embryonic development of *M. aral*

Major Phase	Time (h/min)	Developmental Features
Zygote	0.00	Adhesive, demersal, spherical, transparent
	0.15-0.19	Formation of perivitelline space around the yolk
Cleavage	0.30	Formation of blastodisc at the animal pole, aggregated oil globules at the animal pole, commencement of first cleavage
	0.54-0.59	2nd cleavage, 4-cell
	2.05-2.15	Unequal blastomeres in size, remain in two rows, 8-cell
	2.35-2.40	4th cleavage, 16-cell
	3.00-4.25	Rapid successive division and transformation into 32, 64, 128 celled stage and so on
Morula	6.40-6.50	Formation of cap at the animal pole, increasing in size
Blastula	10.45-11.05	Marginal blastomeres lose boundaries, compressed
Gastrulation	15.00-15.30	Blastoderm forms thin layer by invading yolk, development of germinal ring, blastoderm covers $\frac{1}{2}$ of yolk, visible embryonic shield, blastoderm covers $\frac{3}{4}$ of yolk
Organogenesis	25.20-25.50	Visible embryonic body, finished yolk invasion, visible undeveloped head and tail, distinguished head and tail, beating heart noticeable, notochord evident
Hatching	30.47- 35.10	Increased twisting movement, embryo breaks egg pod

Figure 1: Different embryonic development stages of *M. aral*: a. zygote, b. cleavage, c. morula, d. blastula, e. gastrula, f. organogenesis, and g. hatching phases

Discussions:

The present study elucidates the successful artificial breeding and meticulously documents the embryonic ontogeny of *Macrogynathus aral*. It was previously hypothesized that simulation of natural environmental conditions under confined captive conditions may trigger spawning [9]. Current findings lend partial validation to established theories, confirming successful gonadal maturation of the species under controlled captivity. Nevertheless, natural spawning did not occur despite captive conditions. To date, [10] and [11] carried out captive breeding of *M. aral* in India via synthetic hormones (Spawn Pro), while [12] employed carp pituitary extract for the same species in Bangladesh. [13] induced spawning in captive *M. aculeatus* using Ovaprim, while [9] achieved breeding success in *M. pancalus* with Ovasis hormone. Similarly, [14], [15], and [16] reported captive breeding and seed production for *M. pancalus*. In this study, Ovatide dosages for male *M. aral* ranged from 0.2-1.0 ml/kg body weight, and for females from 0.4-1.2 ml/kg body weight across all trials, tested at male-to-female ratios of 1:1, 2:1, and 3:1; dosages based from [9]. [17] reported that female fish typically require higher hormone doses than males. Among all experimental treatments, Ovatide hormone at a 2:1 male-to-female ratio yielded the highest fertilization and hatching rates. This M:F ratio of 2:1 proved superior to other configurations in induced breeding trials, consistent with findings by [10]. In *M. aral*, the latency period spanned 15-18 h across varying Ovatide doses and experimental setups, contrasting with the shorter 12-14 h range reported by [11] for the same species and the longer 20-24 h observed by [9] in *M. pancalus*. In *M. aral*, the shortest latency period (15 h) occurred in experiment E2 (T3) with Ovatide doses of 0.6 ml/kg for males and 0.8 ml/kg for females; this aligns with [18], who linked variable dopamine modulation in fish to specific hormone concentrations. Stable water quality in experimental tanks supported high fertilization and hatching rates in *M. aral*. Parameters across GnRH-treated setups (E1-E3)- including temperatures of 27.9-28.3°C, salinity (0.018-0.025 ppt), pH 7.78-8.12, dissolved oxygen 5.67-5.95 ppm, free CO₂ 1.98-2.26 ppm, alkalinity 88.7-95.6 ppm, and total hardness 91.2-102.8 ppm, coincided with robust spawning performance. [10] reported similar efficacy with slightly warmer temperatures (30.2-32.5°C) and pH 7.6-7.8 during successful *M. aral* breeding. According to [10], *M. aral* shows batch spawning behavior, with oviposition lasting 2 hours. In Experiment 2 (T3), female *M. aral* recorded the highest egg deposition at approximately 2550 eggs each, while Experiment 1 (T4) recorded the lowest at approximately 660 eggs per female.

Fish are ectothermic animals, meaning they rely on external sources to regulate their body temperature, and water temperature serves as a primary environmental cue for their development. Higher temperatures can increase the metabolic rate of embryos, leading to faster cell division and organogenesis. This can result in quicker hatching times and shorter gestation periods. The water parameters recorded in this study were found to be suitable for the species under investigation. The present study recorded water temperatures of 27.9 to 28.3°C during embryonic development in *M. aral*, similar to the 28-29°C reported by [7] for *M. aculeatus* and the 27-31°C noted by [8] for *M. pancalus*. Egg characteristics in *M. aral* closely matched those from prior studies. Unfertilized eggs were dense, demersal, and sticky, while fertilized eggs were round, transparent, and adhesive. These features align with findings by [8]. [16] described fertilized eggs of *M. pancalus* as rounded to oval, transparent, demersal, sticky, and yellowish-brown. Fertilized eggs in Mastacembelidae generally share a spherical shape and adhesiveness, though *M. aculeatus* eggs showed a distinct green color [7]. In contrast, the present study observed green colored fertilized eggs in *M. aral*, as supported by [10]. Variations in egg coloration across Mastacembelidae may arise from genetic differences or environmental influences, such as diet and water quality, on pigment formation. In this study, fertilized egg diameters in *M. aral* ranged from 1.25-1.60 mm. [10] reported larger sizes of 2.46-2.65 mm for the same species. By comparison, [8] measured 0.70-1.30 mm in *M. pancalus*, while [16] noted 1.51±0.005 mm in *M. pancalus*. [7] observed 1.20-1.40 mm in *M. aculeatus*, and [19] found 1.50-2.02 mm in *Mastacembelus mastacemblus*.

Embryonic development patterns in Mastacembelidae species closely mirrored those documented in prior studies; nonetheless, notable inter- and intraspecific variations emerged in developmental timelines, with some species exhibiting comparable initiation but divergent progression rates. In *M. aral*, the present study revealed blastodisc formation commencing at the animal pole within 30 min post-fertilization (PF), aligning

closely with observations in *M. aculeatus* [7], [20], [21], and *M. pancalus* [8], [22]. However, [23] noted an earlier onset at 15 min PF in *M. aculeatus*, whereas [19] reported a delay of approximately 4 h in *Mastacembelus mastacembelus*. Cleavage completion occurred by 4.25 h PF in our study, matching reports for *M. pancalus* [8], [22], though it was slightly faster at 3.3 h PF in *M. aculeatus* [7], and 4.17 h PF as per [21]. In the current study, *M. aral* reached the morula stage by 6.50 h PF, the blastula by 11.05 h PF, and the gastrula by 15.30 h PF- timings consistent with *M. aculeatus* findings by [21]. For *M. pancalus*, morula formation occurred at 10.10 h PF [8] and 8.25 h PF [22], while in *M. aculeatus* it appeared earlier at 4.10 h PF [7]. Embryonic body emergence, with approximately 3/4th of the yolk enveloped by the blastoderm, took 27.15 h PF in *M. pancalus* [22] and 24.30 h PF [8], compared to 15.12 h PF [21] or 25.30 h PF [7] in *M. aculeatus*. In the present study, *M. aral* embryos showed distinct head and tail regions by 25.50 h PF, with heart pulsations evident at the same time and hatching at 35.10 h PF. These findings closely related with hatching at 30-32 h PF reported for the same species by [10]. Head/tail differentiation appeared later in *M. pancalus* at 29.20 h PF and 31.30 h PF [8], [22] while hatching times varied across related spiny eels: 35.00-41.00 h PF in *M. pancalus* [8], [22], [24] and 31.45-34.17 h PF in *M. aculeatus* [7], [21].

Conclusion:

This research confirms the efficacy of Ovotide, a synthetic hormone, in triggering successful spawning and embryonic progression in the ornamental spiny eel *M. aral* within controlled captive environments. Administering 0.8 ml/kg body weight to females and 0.6 ml/kg body weight to males produced strong outcomes in spawning rates, egg fertilization, and larval hatching, paving the way for a reliable breeding blueprint moving forward. By easing reliance on overexploited natural stocks, these protocols promote sustainable seed supply for the ornamental aquaculture sector. Their affordability makes them accessible to backyard farmers, resource-limited growers, and women-led ventures in areas such as West Bengal, driving economic opportunities alongside habitat protection. Success hinged on fine-tuned elements like balanced male-female ratios, stable water conditions, and vigilant post-spawn handling, highlighting the value of holistic care strategies. Future studies should scale these approaches for commercial operations in varied climates and investigate selective breeding to boost offspring resilience.

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